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The Impact of Indirect Translation on Balochi Literary Texts: A Study of Notes from Underground

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ABSTRACT

Indirect translation has been a consistent feature of Balochi literature since the inception of translating in Balochi, providing access to international literary genres and thematic nuances. However, this practice has hardly been the focus of attention in the academic discourse. This study critically examines the challenges posed by the indirect or relay translation, particularly its impacts on the fidelity with the source text and cultural nuances of the source culture. Using Fyodor Dostoevsky's *Notes from Underground* as a case study, the study demonstrates how a middle- language distorts the philosophical underpinnings and nuances in the ultimate target text Balochi. However, though indirect translation has its merits and it has provided Balochi literature with access to diverse international literary genres and thematic nuances, its contributions are accompanied by challenges that require critical academic attention. This study acknowledges the historical role of indirect translation in enriching the Balochi literature, along with highlighting the significant risks it poses to textual fidelity, cultural misrepresentation, and philosophical nuances. By addressing these limitations, the research study recommends and emphasizes for more first-hand or direct translations to preserve the integrity and depth of the source text and the intent of the author. Employing a qualitative descriptive approach, the study recommends strategies to minimize linguistic and cultural compromises. By addressing these issues, this research work aims to foster more rigorous translation practices in Balochi literature.

Key words: Translation Studies, Indirect Translation, Second-hand Translation, English, Urdu, Balochi, *Notes from Underground*

Introduction

Translation has, always, had its complexities. It is not a simple and mere operation of meaning transportation between languages; rather, a simplest linguistic form and a cultural element needs mastery of linguistic and cultural competence to transfer the same from one language to the other. Yet again, complete translation is still a mirage. Willis Barnstone (quoted in Washbourne, 608:2013) defines translation as a “frequently a historical process of creating originals”, however, retaining the original essence of the source text in the target

text is itself challenging for a translator. However, despite such serious challenges and hard-work, translation is still regarded as an activity inferior to the original creative work, particularly, with respect to literary translations.

Hillaire Belloc, quoted in Bijay Kumar (2005), posits that the art of translation has never been regarded with its due status, regarding it as a secondary and subsidiary art deriving from some other sources. Such derogatory remarks and underestimation of translation has always had negative effects to the due status and value of translation. Such criticism and misunderstandings have not only marginalized the art of translation, but it has, also, escalated their misunderstanding of the importance of and difficulty involved in translation. However, apart from these critical remarks about translation the Brazilian critic Haroldo de Campose (2017) believes that translation is a mode of reading and a critique essential to literary practices and production. To delve into the depths of literature and literary history, one needs to engage in studying the literature in a multitude of languages.

Language and literature are the two most important parts of a man's everyday life, and the importance of translation cannot be denied in anyway in language and literature. It is believed that the absence and lack of translation in a language and

literature implies that the said language and literature have still not been freed from the shackles of their primitive past. She further opines that such absence of translation foretells a bleak future for the languages and literatures.

Dr. Abdul Saboor Baloch (2012) in the foreword of his anthology of translated short stories 'آثار' thinks that the reason why Balochi fiction in general, and short story in particular, have gained considerable momentum in creating a niche for themselves in Balochi literature, is because of the translations from foreign languages, especially from literatures whose short stories have proved themselves in the world literature.

Literary translation is like providing fresh oxygen to the smaller literatures, which helps them defy the dangers of stagnation. Hence, it is advisable that such operation may be conducted by experts to extract the soul from the body of the source language and penetrate it in the body of the target language to make it breathe. However, in translating, it is inevitable that all texts suffer some damage in being translated from one language to another, and one would imagine that an effort would be made to keep this damage to minimum. To minimize the loss of the original text's theme and meaning, it is important that the translation may be carried out without a mediating language, as posited "... it would seem incumbent on all involved to ensure that any literary work subject to this awful process at least be re-presented in English by the most direct route possible...i.e., translated directly from the original" (Twice Removed, vol. IV).

Literary translations in Balochi literature began during 1950s. Dr. Abdul Saboor Baloch (2012:07) writes about the beginning of translations in Balochi literature as:

پشومانين جيئن ايم ميگس گوركي/عبدالصمد اميري، ماھانگه، اومان ڪراچي (مارچ 1952) ڪه مني پٽ ۽ ٻول ۽ رندا اے بلوچي ۽ اولي رجيننگين آزمائڪ ايتا

According to his research Maxim Gorky's 'Pashomanen Zaal' (پشومانين ڏال) which is attributed to Maxim Gorky, is the first short-story translated into Balochi, which was translated by Abdul Samad Amiri in 1952, and it was published in the monthly magazine Auman in March, 1952 (though the researcher did not find any such story from Maxim Gorky, hence, unable to mention its English or Russian version).

However, talking about the Balochi translations Naguman (2013) comments that it is very unfortunate that there are no language experts to "directly translate" Russian, French or English short stories into Balochi or the other way round. This gap is filled through Urdu language only.

Though such 'indirect or second-hand translation' has helped Balochi literature bring in new literary genres and ideas; however, such indirectness sometimes results in a differently new creation or giving birth to a text which does not resemble with the original text very closely. "ITr (indirect translation) tends to be negatively evaluated because it arguably increases the distance to the ultimate ST and, therefore, is often hidden or camouflaged" (Alexandra, 2017:01).

The prime objective of a translation is to introduce the target language and culture with the socio- linguistic, socio-cultural and socio-political norms of the original language and culture, however, at times, in place of meeting the objectives of translation, the linguistic and cultural gaps and differences are widened due to indirect translation, which itself is "translation of a translation" (ibid). It is because the linguistic system and the culture of language 'A' differs with language 'B', and the linguistic system and culture of 'C' differs with both 'A' and 'B'. Resultantly, the gaps are widened and the differences are misunderstood and wrongly rendered.

Though indirect translation has been there for ages and the languages, literatures, and cultures have benefited from this type of translation for centuries, yet again, "ITr has always been considered the choice of last resort no matter how common or natural it may be" (Wenjie, 2017:182).

The study analyzed the possible reasons of failure of creating master pieces and trying new literary genres in Balochi literature, due to the indirect translations, resulting misrepresentation of the actual thought, ideology, form, and meaning of the original source text.

Objectives

To critically analyze specific passages from the English, Urdu, and Balochi versions of Notes from Underground to highlight how indirect translation distorts or shifts meaning.

To examine how the original tone of the English text, particularly its existential irony and philosophical depth, is impacted by the intermediary translation into Urdu and its subsequent translation into Balochi.

To explore and recommend strategies that translators can adopt to preserve the essence of the original text while working with indirect translations, balancing cultural adaptation and fidelity.

Research Questions

The study was undertaken to address the following research questions, which, when answered, helped the researcher achieve the study's aims and objectives:

What risks does indirect translation pose to the meaning of the original source text?

How significantly does indirect translation alter the meaning of the original source text in translation of a translation?

What strategies can be employed to preserve the original source text's message and meaning in indirect translation?

Literature Review

Indirect Translation

The phenomenon of indirect translation has been there for ages. The concept of translation from Language A to B and then from B to C is termed differently by different scholars and authors. For Toury (1995) it is "second-hand translation", "relay-translation" for Dollerup (2000), "mediated translation" for Pym (2011) and Washbourne (2013). However, they all mean the same thing by calling it differently "translation of a translation" (Gambier, 1994).

In the sarcastic comments of Barnstone about translation that it is "frequently a historical process of creating original" (1993:141) by quipping this he was talking about the art of a text that concealed its own status as a translation. Though he sarcastically commented that but there arise unsuspected insights from his comments in cases of translations of translations, that is, indirect translations, which can be defined as translations, partial translations or adaptations that serve as an acknowledged or unacknowledged new source text.

Indirect translations have always been a common practice among the translators' community, particularly in literary translations. About the widespread of indirect translation in literary translations, Dollerup (2000:21) pointed out that indirect translation in literary translations is "indeed so common that, in literary studies, it is hardly noted at all." Though such indirectness is hardly taken care of in literary translations, however, it has always been considered as a Hobson's choice no matter how common or natural it may look. However, despite its reputation as being secondary or mediated "it has been crucial to the dissemination of literatures of non-major cultures or in less-spoken languages" (Wenjie, 2017:2). Despite the secondary status of indirection translations in translation studies, this is unsuspected fact that the

indirect translation has played an important role in creating a world literature, and it has also helped comparative literary and linguistic studies. As Wenjie (2017) believes had it not been for the indirect translation the world literature would have not known the different literary genres that have reached to peripheral literatures through mediating texts.

Indirect translations are treated differently across cultures. In cultures like Balochi where there is a great dearth of accessibility to direct literary creations, particularly that of French, German, Italian, Argentinian, Arabic and English literary creations; in such a scenario having the facility of reading a literary master piece which passes through three or four languages and then reaches to them is a blessing, such as from French, to English to Urdu and lastly to Balochi. Theo Hermans (1999) says that “[T]he rules permitting or forbidding translation from an intermediate language rather than from the original source language vary over time as well as cross-culturally and in relation to particular genres and source language” (75).

In comparison with direct translation, indirect translation is more complex and hybrid in nature. Alexandra Rosa (2017) believes that if a direct translation is deemed bad, the indirect translation is even worse than that. Talking about Balochi translations Naguman (2013) reiterates that there may come new ideas and techniques in Balochi short story writing, however; such indirect translations will not be able to retain the taste and the feel of the original source text. A story first created in Russian, then translated into English, thereon translated into Urdu and, lastly, from Urdu to Balochi, will, surely, lose its readability, and its actual story.

Despite such serious allegations on indirect translations it is still widely practiced and as for the reasons why translators opt for indirect translations, it is, more or less, due to a lack of translators or of linguistic competence in the ultimate source language, or due to the difficulty obtaining the original text or translating from a geographically and/or structurally distant language. The higher the price of translating from a distant language, as well as power relations between languages, cultures and agents within the world translation systems are also mentioned as possible causes for indirect translations (see for example Washbourne 2013).

Notes from Underground

Fyodor Dostoevsky, the Russian novelist, emerged in 19th century, realized way too earlier than his contemporaries that hazards the world was about to experience due to their “naïve belief in a coming technological Utopia.” (Cogswell, 28:2008) Dostoevsky in his works portrayed the classic problems of existentialism. His novella *Notes from Underground*, which was first published in 1864, for instance deals with an existential point of view, “beginning with the unreliability of reason”. However, man is allured with logic and rationality, Dostoevsky claims that originally man is not a logical creature he rather believed that what triggers man’s choice, is not just most “advantageous advantage” but a “free-will” as his choices are not always guided alone from his rational side but also is a manifestation of his impulses and desires. He says “and how these wiseacres know that man wants a normal, a virtuous choice? What has made them conceive that man must want a rationally advantageous choice? What man wants is simply independent choice, whatever that independence may cost and wherever it may lead” (Cogswell, 30).

In *Notes from the Underground* the protagonist consistently and repeatedly deals with inner conflicts, self-contradictions, self-pity which engrosses his mind so rigorously that his life becomes an embodiment of an unknown suffering. The work openly declares the paradox of human mind. *Underground* man exists without any sort of

sanctuary and refuge from the pain and agony of modern consciousness.

Review of the Related Literatures

Many translation scholars such as Zheng (1998) think that translating through a mediating language is quite risky, and such translation will risk the fidelity of translation. Although, in many countries, such as in China, indirect translation has been legitimized due to a dearth of translators with linguistic competence of less-spoken languages, it is thought of a lesser choice. A text translated indirectly is prone to inherit errors from the mediating texts. If in the mediating text there is any mistranslation and the source text has not been translated properly, then, difference from the original source text and the end product resulted from a mediating text will be two-fold. Rendering through a mediating text “will inevitably produce differences that more often than not increase the distance from the ST” (Ringmar, 2007:10) and an indirect translation is thus two steps away from the original source text.

Literary translations began in Balochi after the second half of the 20th century, when some literary active men began translating the Russian and French master pieces in Balochi through Urdu or English. *پشومانين دال* is the first short-story to be translated in Balochi, which is authored by Maxim Gorky, and translated into Balochi by Abdul Samad Amiri (Baloch, 2012), however, the researcher could not find any such short-story from Maxim Gorky, hence unable to name the short-story’s English or Russian title. While translating novels and novellas began in 1967 and the first novel to be translated is Ernest Hemingway’s *Old Man and the Sea* which was translated by Ghous Baksh Sabir, who translated the novel from Urdu (Baloch, 2009).

Dr. Abdul Saboor Baloch (2009) in his PhD dissertation (*پٽ ۽ ٻول ۽ نڪ*) (Balochi Fiction: Research and Criticism) says that the translated novels in Balochi literature are more in number than the novels written in Balochi. Most of these novels are (indirectly) translated from Urdu into Balochi, and very few novels are directly translated from their original source languages to Balochi which include Leo Tolstoy’s *Hadji Murat*, Noor Mohammad Taraki’s *De Bang Musafiri*, Amarta Pritam’s novel *Korey Kagaz*, *Shama e Azadi* by Ikramullah, and the Persian novel *Bof Kor* by Sadiq Hidayat.

Though these (indirect-translations) have a huge contribution in motivating the Baloch literary men to write novels and novellas in Balochi literature, however, the meaning of the original source texts have at times paid the price for such indirectness. Dr. Bezan Saba (2012) in the foreword of his translation of the *Stranger* (translated from English into Balochi), though an indirect translation, reiterates that the need of the hour is that the literary creations of other literatures should be directly translated from English into Balochi and the translation of *The Stranger* is a small effort in this regard.

Albert Camus’s philosophical work about the absurdity of life *L’Étranger* is translated into British English as *The Outsider* and *The Stranger* in US English. The said novel has two translations in Balochi as *درآمد* one translated from English into Balochi and the other from Urdu to Balochi. The

names of the characters in the translation from Urdu to Balochi have been disguised to the degree that if a reader encounters the same in English may get confused as to how the characters of the same novel are different in its English and Balochi versions. For example, Meursault is the protagonist of the said novel. His name in Urdu translation is *مرسو* (Marso) and the translator from Urdu to Balochi has also named him the same: *مرسو*, however, the translator from English to

Balochi has somewhat retained the phonetic similarity in his translation with that of English Meursault as میورسال (Meursal). Moreover, the names of the other characters such as Marie, Raymond and Masson are also disguised as ماری, رے مو, and موسیو respectively.

In a novel like *The Stranger* in which each sentence and the selection of each word is important because each word, phrase or sentence reveals the inner world of Meursault and influences the flow of events in the novel, hence, deleting any such word or phrase may cause a misinterpretation of Meursault's inner world. See for example:

English:

“At first I did not take him quite seriously” (*The Stranger*, p.40) English to Balochi (p.61):

”بندت ےء من مردکار ےء نیمگا زیات دلگوش نہ دات“ (Bindata mn mardkar ey nemaga ziyat dilgosh nadat)

However, because the Urdu translator has opted to skip this sentence (p.60), hence the translator from Urdu to Balochi, Sharaf Shad, has also skipped the same (p.81). Such deletion techniques and skipping of sentences in a philosophical novel may hinder the natural flow of the novel along with a misrepresentation of the character's inner world and his approach to the events.

Naguman (2013) in his book نگانک (Nagdaank) criticizes indirect translations and mockingly says in such translations by the time the text reaches a third or fourth language, will lose all its sweetness and pleasant essence and becomes stale. The translation of Aristotle's *Poetics* via Urdu into Balochi is an example of such stale text. Though not a literary translation, however, due to the indirectness or may be, due to translator's choice, it seems like an addition of a 'stale translation' in Balochi, translated by A.R. Dad (2009). *Poetics* is translated into Urdu as بوطیقا by Aziz Ahmed and as شعر ےء ےء ےء in Balochi (literally *The Art of Poetry*). The Balochi translator has chosen to apply the deletion technique of translation in which he has squeezed the book to mere 42 pages, however, its Urdu translation is way thicker and things are elaborated more extensively than its Balochi, from which it can be assumed that the translator has followed his own suit in the translation of the *Poetics*.

As for the misrepresentation of original thought see for example:

English

“...even a woman may be good, and also a slave; though the woman may be said to be an inferior being and the slave quite worthless” (p.23)

English to Urdu (p.78)

”ایک عورت یا غلام کے اطوار بھی اچھے ہو سکتے ہیں، حالانکہ بالعموم عورت کے اطوار تو شاید اچھے سے زیادہ بُرے ہوتے ہیں اور غلام کے بالکل بُرے“.

Urdu to Balochi

”گلام یا جنین ہم نیکیں مردمے بیت کنتہ راستی ےء بچارے جنین جھلڑیں مردمے ےء گلام سیلے“

(...ghulam ya janin ham neken mardumey beet kant. Rasti a bechary janin jahlteren mardumey o ghulam silley)

The Balochi translation, if back-translated into English will mean something different. The back-translation of the same is ...slave or woman can be good. But the reality is woman is an inferior being and the slave a vile. The arrangement of words such as in English woman precedes slave and the same arrangement has been made in Urdu. Moreover, in both, English and Urdu translations, the probability of woman as being inferior to man has been shown, while the Balochi translation is quite sexist and declares all the woman as inferior to men. A reader of this translation will always believe that Aristotle discriminated between men and woman and always treated the woman as an inferior being, until the reader happens to read the original or a direct translation of the same. However, the Urdu translator has rendered the same quite well.

Though indirect translation is inevitable and the Balochi literature has, immensely,

benefited from it, however, on the other hand it has done significant damage to the original source texts that have been translated indirectly to Balochi. And given the limited availability of translators proficient in languages like French, Russian, and German, Balochi literature often depends on Urdu or English as intermediaries. Such dependency is the rationale behind examining the challenges and limitations indirect translation poses, more importantly examination of cultural misrepresentation and potential loss of textual meaning. Moreover, there is no questioning the fact that indirect translation is an immediate solution to the language barriers the translators face, it is very important that Balochi literature meets the international standards of trans-creations due to its growing recognition on global platforms.

This research, therefore, is conducted to find out the linguistic and cultural compromises, forced by indirect translation, and advocate for more and more direct translation efforts within the Balochi literary community. It is sought to bring forth and educate translators, readers, and literary scholars about the challenges and drawbacks of indirect translation, ultimately fostering an awareness of best practices to preserve the authenticity and artistic essence of original works in Balochi literature.

Research Methodology

This study examines the impact of indirect translations on Balochi literary texts through a case study of *Notes from Underground* by 19th-century existentialist Fyodor Dostoevsky. The novel was translated into Urdu by Farkhi as ایک پاگل کی ڈائری and subsequently into Balochi by Dr. Ali Dost as ڳوٺڪي ۽ روڊپٽر. Both titles translate into English as *A Madman's Diary*. A qualitative-descriptive and evaluative approach was adopted to address the research questions and achieve the objectives of this research work.

Data Collection

According to Wenjie (2017), "Studies in indirect translation tend to be large in scale, covering a comparatively long period and involving multi-level research, including micro-, meso-, and macro- perspectives" (p. 183). Given the complexity of indirect translation, however, this study analyzed *Notes from Underground* synchronically, focusing on sociocultural and linguistic aspects, using corpus-assisted methods. For this case study, data was randomly collected from all 21 chapters of the novel, focusing on the English as source text, Urdu as the mediating text, and Balochi as the target text. Sixteen samples, starting from first to last, were selected at random with half presented in a tabular format for comparative analysis.

Micro Level: Individual sentences were analyzed for linguistic shifts.

Meso Level: Cultural and thematic aspects were evaluated to identify sociocultural influences.

The *Notes from Underground* was selected because it is one of the recent novels which was translated indirectly from Urdu to Balochi. Moreover, it was also selected because it is known by the researcher that the translator has a strong command of English, which could influence the translation choices.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The collected data from *Notes from Underground* was back-translated into the original source language, bypassing the mediating language (Urdu). This allowed for a direct comparison between the source and the target texts to evaluate changes in word choices, sentence structure, alterations in the existential and philosophical underpinnings of the source text, and identifying whether shifts occurred due to the

				reduced to a plain statement of inaction.
70	They all dropped me, and I sat crushed and annihilated. ... Of course, I stayed.	ہماری طرف کسی نے توجہ نہ کی اور میں خاموشی سے اپنی نکت برداشت کرتا رہا... بے شک میں ان کے ساتھ ٹریک رہا ہوں۔	میں نے تمہارا کس سے ٹکڑوں کو گر نہ کرنا ہے من گھڑی خاموشی ہے وہی ہے عزتی سنگ آتش... بے شک من گھڑی ایشال ہوا ہونگ اور۔	Tone Difference: The ironic self-awareness in English is transformed into a tone of resigned humility in Urdu.
90	For a long time already I'd sensed that I had turned her whole soul over and broken her heart and the more convinced of it I was, the more I wished to reach my goal quickly and as forcefully as possible. It was the game, the game that fascinated me; not just the game, however . . .	Translatio missing, n page no.12	Because the translation, in Urdu, is missing, hence missing in Balochi as well.	Translation Gap: Emotional depth in the ST is not conveyed due to missing translation.
107	I was going to lie right now... I opened her hand and put... in it out of malice	ہاتھ صاف گولی سے کام لیتے ہوتے ہیں بتانا چلتا ہوں کہ میں نے اس کی ہاتھ کھول کر اس میں کچھ رقم رکھ دی تھی، یہ میرے خبیث باطن کا اظہار تھا۔	ہیشکا میں سب سب گنگ لوٹیں کہ میں اتنی ٹسٹ و تہا چیزے زر اور گرتنگ آتہ۔ اے منی حبیث این باطن و درشان آتہ۔	Meaning Nuance: "Malice" in English is softened to "باطن خبیث" (ill intent), reducing its sharpness.

The ultimate target text, which is Balochi in this case, is an indirect translation translated via Urdu instead of English, has many facets of semantic and tonal differences. It is due to this indirect or relay approach of translation that the subtle nuances carried by the English text are either left out or mistranslated. Had the translation into Balochi been a direct approach, the ultimate product would not have

reflected the linguistic choices of the Urdu translator, instead it would have taken the reader into the original author's intent. Here is how utilizing an indirect approach in translation of literary texts impacted the ultimate target text:

The Urdu translation is an interpretation of the English text, however, it can often be seen that the translator has tried to remain morally judgmental by incorporating adjectives, descriptive details, and cultural norms which refer to moral judgments. Take for example the word wicked, the translator, instead of a one-word equivalent of the same, expanded it into (malice, hostility, resentment, envy, and animosity), and altered the sharp and ironic self-assessment in the English into a moralistic and explicit depiction. Hence, the translator into Balochi has followed the Urdu translator, without consulting the nearest direct translation of the original, therefore, recreated a literary text which is void of the semantic and tonal originality. The English phrase I am a wicked man, for instance, is translated as (my heart is filled with envy, resentment, and animosity), which is a direct reflection of the Urdu phrase instead of reflecting the English source text's literariness and simplicity. While reading the novel it is felt that the English narrator's tone is terse, ironic, and self-critical, reflecting the existential absurdity of his condition. Words like wicked are intentionally vague, allowing readers to infer the nature of the narrator's self-loathing. While in the Balochi version of the novel the tone shifts to one of moral self-condemnation and emotional heaviness, directly mirroring Urdu's moralistic style. As a result, the understated and sharp irony, which are the two characteristics of the source text, are missing in the ultimate target text.

Furthermore, there is this phrase in the same paragraph that I think my liver hurts which in Urdu is translated as میرا دل بھی چھلی چھلی ہے and the same in Balochi is literally translated as ہم ٹُکر ٹُکر انت منی دل, which when back-translated reads as my heart is also pierced into pieces, clearly portraying Urdu's influence on the translator's interpretation and choice of words. This illustrates how indirect translation, whether intentional or not, forces meaning, tonal and cultural differences. The reference to liver pain in English, for example, is literal, which strongly suggests author's self-mockery and detached tone regarding his physical health. Both, Urdu and Balochi, translations have rendered this physical illness into a metaphor which translate into English as heartbreak. Instead of translating the same literally, the Urdu translator translated the same figuratively, and the Balochi translator also followed the suit. Therefore, equating a physical organ, liver, with a metaphorical and symbolic organ in Urdu and Balochi, heart, responsible for feelings and emotions rather than physical health. Moreover, the phrases چھلی چھلی in Urdu and ٹُکر ٹُکر in Balochi evoke imagery of emotional devastation, commonly used to

describe heartbreak or betrayal. This shifts the meaning from physical discomfort to emotional suffering, which is entirely absent in the source text.

It is observed that the Balochi text inherits this metaphorical reinterpretation from Urdu, losing the specificity and mundanity of the English original. Instead of reflecting the protagonist's ironic detachment, the translation dramatizes his condition as emotional pain, which was never intended by the source text.

In page no.21 of English text while the narrator talks about his desire to become an insect he says I'll tell you solemnly that I wanted many times to become an insect. But I was not deemed worthy even of that. The same in page no.8 in the Balochi translation is rendered as من یک کر مے بیوتین اتوں بلے بلکہ منی انکس ارزشت نہ انت من شمارا اے گشیں کہ منی باز رندا واپش بوتگ کہ درینگین when back-translated would read as I tell you this that it's been my wish many times that I wished I were an

insect, but maybe I am not that important. As is evident from the back-translation, the Balochi text, due to its being indirectly translated through a mediating text reduces the emotional intensity and existential irony of the English original. This translation has reduced the author's self-critical and alienated voice, creating a text faraway from Dostoevsky's existential themes. Moreover, the translator of the ultimate target text fails to portray a philosopher in crisis, rather he rendered the philosophical nuances of the source text into mere themes of honor and inferiority. Although, the readers of the text might better relate themselves to such themes, it has surely harmed the source text's philosophical underpinnings and nuances.

Talking about his preference for "conscious inertia", the author in page no. 43 of English text he reiterates that The final end, gentlemen: better conscious inertia! And so, long live the underground! However, the Balochi translation of the same sentence, in page no.41, rendered via

Urdu text has been translated as کسے گوئڈ! ٹوک چوش انت کہ چیزے نا چیزے کنگ شریں گئے، استارانی علم ۽ رد ۽ زانکاری ۽۔
 -اگہی یک ۽ مصیبت ہے۔ when back-translated reads as to cut the long story short, the thing is it is better to do something than nothing. According to astronomical theory knowledge and knowing are troublesome.

From the back-translation of the ultimate target text, which is Balochi, into English, it is evident that the translation has drifted, semantically and tonally, from its original English roots. It can be gauged via these shifts that how far can indirect translation warp an author's core intent and message, at times even going to the extent of reversing the author's intent. As is evident in Dostoevsky's argument for conscious inertia, however, the same is equated with an almost opposite sentiment in the back-translated Balochi text, suggesting action over inaction. Moreover, the mention of concepts like astronomical theory creates further the distraction from philosophical depth of Dostoevsky's work. Moreover, the existentialist delicacies and the characteristics of the English text, treated as the source text, are substituted with distorted and even contradictory ideas, which has significantly damaged the philosophical sophistication, probably due to interpretative choices made during the indirect translation process.

Omitting a portion of a text in a philosophical and existential novel like Notes from Underground when translating most probably dilute the integrity of the work The Notes from Underground is a fiction thoroughly based on the principles of existential philosophy, in which each of its passage contributes to the intricate web of ideas, themes, and the narrator's psychological subtlety. Omitting any of its part involves a great text risk of mistranslating the text, which can cost the translator the meaning of the source text, and undermining the philosophical and existential nuances, and potentially misrepresenting the author's intent.

Koby and Lacruz (2018) in their article, The Thorny Problem of Translation and Interpreting Quality, highlight the problems affecting the translation quality and underline the importance of preserving the integrity of the source text. Particularly talking about the literary translation, they (2018) do not recommend omitting parts of a text, which according to them may severely harm and distort the "authenticity and intellectual rigor" of the original work. More importantly, the existential, and/or philosophical underpinnings of a literary text are a must not to be omitted part of the text, as they significantly contribute to the author's intent and thematic depth of the text. However, Balochi translation omitted an important passage present in page no.90 of the English text— "For a long time already I'd sensed that I had turned her whole soul over and broken her heart, and the more convinced of it I was, the more I wished to reach my goal quickly and as forcefully as possible. It was the game, the

game that fascinated me; not just the game, however . . .” Because Urdu translation omitted this passage, hence the Balochi translation, probably unaware of such omission, omitted the same. However, the omission of the this semantically significant passage has severely disrupted the pragmatic and communicative flow of the ultimate target text. Thanks to the omission of the said moment of confession and sadistic gratification, the translation has failed to capture the complexity of the author's internal conflict and the dynamics of manipulation and remorse, which are central to the novel's existential exploration.

Discussion: Addressing Objectives and Research Questions

The objectives of this research study were successfully achieved, and all the research questions were also addressed. The study critically analyzed the impacts of indirect translation by selecting Dostoevsky's Notes from Underground. Based on the findings valuable insights are drawn regarding the preservation of tonal, semantic and pragmatics, and cultural nuances and thematic essence of the source text in Balochi as the target text. The findings and recommendations underscore the dire need for direct translations, suggesting that for the sake of honoring the linguistic and cultural nuances international literary works in regional languages like Balochi. Henceforth, the study's findings are discussed with reference to the objectives and research questions of the study.

Objective 1:

To critically analyze specific passages from the English, Urdu, and Balochi versions of Notes from Underground to highlight how indirect translation distorts or shifts meaning.

Sixteen (16), randomly, selected samples sentences, from all three versions of Notes from Underground, that is English, Urdu, and Balochi, were compared for the purpose of identifying semantic and pragmatic, tonal and cultural nuances inherent in the first language. As discussed and presented earlier, the English text is replete with and characterizes existential irony and absurdity, however, the same were not translated with equal philosophical rigor. Instead, the thematic nuances and philosophical characteristics of the English source texts are found to be rendered as mere reflection of unworthiness following what the Urdu translation has done with the author's intent. Moreover, the author's preference for philosophical ideas such as conscious inertia was altered into entirely different sentiment advocating action instead of inaction in the Balochi text, significantly distorting the philosophical intent. Through this analysis, the said objective is effectively met by examining how indirect translation results in creating layers of mistranslation through the mediating texts.

Objective 2:

To examine how the original tone of the English text, particularly its existential irony and philosophical depth, is impacted by the intermediary translation into Urdu and its subsequent translation into Balochi.

A recurring pattern of shifts was observed in the study. For instance, the tonal characteristics inherent in the English text, such as that of terse, self-critical, and ironic tones in the English text were more often equated with moralistic and emotionally charged tone in both Urdu and Balochi

translations. Refer to the phrase I am a wicked man in English and translated into Balochi as

منی دل کی (my heart is filled with envy, resentment, and animosity)

assigning the text a moralistic feature which is not found in the original. The findings strengthen the idea that how and to what extent indirect translation may distort the tone of the source text, even stripping of the text to their philosophical and thematic intents.

Objective 3:

To explore and recommend strategies that translators can adopt to preserve the essence of the original text while working with indirect translations, balancing cultural adaptation and fidelity.

There is no questioning the fact that Balochi literature has immensely benefited from the indirect translations, however, the study strongly recommends that translators make sure that they consult the original source text when translating indirectly to minimize the risk of mistranslating. At the same time, the study also recommends that translators collaborate with source language experts who may contribute in bridging the linguistic and cultural nuances. Moreover, it is advised that the publishers of the translation products prioritize and demand direct translations to ensure the source text intent is wholly translated. These recommendations, will surely, provide a framework for improving translation practices in Balochi literature.

Answers to Research Questions

What risks does indirect translation pose to the meaning of the original source text?

The study revealed that indirect translation introduces semantic, tonal, and thematic shifts, often distorting the source text's philosophical depth and existential nuances. For example, cultural idioms and moralistic overtones in Urdu influenced the Balochi text, leading to misrepresentation.

How significantly does indirect translation alter the meaning of the original source text in translation of a translation?

The findings showed that meaning alterations were significant. Key existential ideas, such as the preference for "conscious inertia," were completely transformed, impacting the text's philosophical coherence.

What strategies can be employed to preserve the original source text's message and meaning in indirect translation?

The study recommends and suggests reduced over-reliance on indirect translations. Moreover, the study also recommends the prioritization of most direct translation or the source text itself for translation into Balochi language. Apart from this, the study also suggests capacity building trainings and collaborations for translators in order to foster direct translation capabilities.

Implications

The study has its implications on Balochi literature in general and on Balochi translations in particular. The study brought forth some of the important issues with respect to the preservation of the source text meaning and cultural and literary nuances. Moreover, it also recommended frameworks for improved translations, even if the translator is opting for indirect or relay translation in Balochi.

The study revealed the drawbacks of indirect translations, recommended literary translators to prioritize first-hand or direct translations. Such a shift in approach will, surely, enhance the authenticity of translated works, ensuring that foreign literary thoughts and genres are introduced to Balochi literature more effectively. Indirect translations often dilute cultural characteristics as they pass through multiple

languages. This study emphasizes the misrepresentation of the original source text's cultural aspects in second- or third-hand translations. After this paper now the translators shall be more aware of these pitfalls and strive to preserve cultural integrity by avoiding already translated texts.

As seen in the analysis by relying on indirect translations, translators risk compromising the fidelity of the source text, whether intentionally or unintentionally.

This study urges translators to

remain faithful to the original work, fostering a stronger ethical commitment to preserving its thematic and cultural essence.

The study's findings shall inform literary audiences about the importance of direct translations, empowering them to demand higher-quality works. This shift in readership expectations could compel translators and publishers to prioritize direct translations, ultimately enriching Balochi literature and ensuring it retains the depth and authenticity of the original texts.

By addressing these areas, this study has not only contributed to the academic understanding of translation practices but also provided actionable insights to improve the quality and authenticity of translated works in Balochi literature.

Recommendations and Conclusion

Recommendations

This study highlighted the inherent difficulties of translating through a mediating language, particularly in a bid to preserve the complex existential layers of Dostoevsky's *Note from Underground*. These findings serve as the ice-breakers for more comprehensive examination of indirect translation with Balochi literature. The future researchers may explore other literary genres such as poetry, drama, and others, determining these linguistic and cultural shifts are a universal trend in indirect literary translations or they are unique to specific literary forms such as the fiction only. Moreover, conducting interviews or surveys with Balochi translators could help identify the constraints and motivations behind opting for indirect translation. This would provide a deeper understanding of the systemic, cultural, or linguistic factors influencing translation choices.

Conclusion

The findings of this research study demonstrated that indirect or relay translation has significant impact on the ultimate target text Balochi. Dostoevsky's *Notes from Underground* was selected as a case study to find how the source text message and nuances are altered due to indirect translation in Balochi literature. Thus, the study's findings and results demonstrated that how the involvement of a middle-language resulted in semantic and pragmatic, tonal and cultural mistranslation and misrepresentation, as a result harming the philosophical intent and underpinnings of the novel.

Moreover, there is no questioning the fact that Balochi literature has immensely benefitted from the practices of indirect translation, it has caused serious damages to the integrity of the original text. This is evident in the loss of existential irony, philosophical nuance, and thematic cohesion in the Balochi translation. Moreover, omissions, oversimplifications, and cultural reinterpretations, inherent characteristics of indirect translation, underscore the need for more rigorous and direct approaches.

By addressing these challenges and implementing the proposed recommendations, future translations can preserve the richness and complexity of original texts, contributing to the growth and authenticity of Balochi literature. This study serves as

a critical starting point for rethinking translation practices and ensuring that the beauty and depth of global literature are fully realized in Balochi.

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